

TABLE 1(b)—CHEMICAL ANALYSES OF CALCIUM, COPPER HYDROXYLAPATITES AND THEIR SOLID SOLUTIONS

Sample no.	Wt%			Molecular formula	Molar volume ml	G. atom ratio Ca+Cu P	Lattice parameter		Unit cell volume
	Ca	Cu	P				a	c	
1.	39.80	—	18.61	$\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	338.60	1.68	9.37	6.38	522.3
2.	27.39	16.06	17.41	$\text{Ca}_{7.2}\text{Cu}_{2.7}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	347.26	1.67	9.26	6.81	507.2
3.	21.48	23.66	16.89	$\text{Ca}_{6.9}\text{Cu}_{4.1}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	354.83	1.67	9.14	6.74	489.8
4.	14.76	32.30	16.30	$\text{Ca}_{4.2}\text{Cu}_{5.8}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	352.78	1.67	9.03	6.68	474.0
5.	6.02	43.52	15.53	$\text{Ca}_{1.5}\text{Cu}_{8.5}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	350.98	1.67	8.92	6.60	467.7
6	—	51.25	15.00	$\text{Cu}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	347.68	1.67	8.83	6.53	443.0

analyses. The observed value of molar g atomic rates of $\frac{\text{Ca}}{\text{P}}$, $\frac{\text{M}}{\text{P}}$ for the end members and $\frac{\text{Ca}+\text{M}}{\text{P}}$, where $\text{M}=\text{Cu}^{2+}$ or Mn^{2+} were found to be equal to 1.67 (theoretical 1.67) was to indicate the formation of homogeneous solid solutions⁵. The substitution of Ca^{2+} by Mn^{2+} (or Cu^{2+}) contract the unit cell of the apatites which confirm the formation of the solid solutions. Such a contraction with the proportion of MnHA (or CuHA) was evident from the excellent regularity with which the unit cell volume of the samples calculated on the basis of the experimentally determined lattice constants decreased with the proportion of MnHA or CuHA.

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Study on N,N'-Ethylenebis(Salicylaldiminato) Beryllium(II)†

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GREEN and Alexander¹ reported the formation of a hydrated beryllium complex with 'Salen' and assigned a formula $\text{Be}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. Batley and Graddon² studied a number of beryllium

complexes of quadridentate Schiff bases derived from the condensation of salicylaldehyde and ethylenediamine, 1, 3-trimethylenediamine and diamines containing four or six methylene groups in the amine bridge. These authors assigned hydrogen bonded structure and a formula, $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{33}\text{BeN}_4\text{O}_{15}$ to the beryllium-salen complex. Singh and Kumar³ used 'Salen' as a gravimetric reagent for beryllium and assigned a possible formula, $\text{Be}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, to the weighable form of the precipitate. No elemental analysis was, however, reported by them for the hydrated precipitate. In the present paper, we are presenting the preparation of anhydrous beryllium-salen complex along with its ir, pmr, reflectance, mass spectral and TGA data for the first time. Based on these data a polymeric structure can be attributed to the complex.

Experimental

Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, Model 221. The pmr spectra were recorded on Varian Associates, Model T-60, operating at 60 Mc/s with TMS as an internal standard. Reflectance spectrum was recorded on a Unicam SP-500 spectrophotometer using MgCO_3 as standard. Mass spectra were recorded on CEC 21-110B (USA) double focussing mass spectrometer at a voltage 70 eV. TGA and DTA were carried out in a MOM Budapest derivatograph at the heating rate of 10°/min in flowing air atmosphere.

N, N'-ethylenebis(salicylaldimine) was prepared by condensing salicylaldehyde and ethylenediamine in ethanol. The yellow shining product was purified by repeated recrystallisation.

Beryllium complex was prepared by reacting an acid solution of 'salen' [(2.68 g, 0.01 mole, dissolved in a few ml of acetic acid (~5 ml), 25 ml alcohol and diluting with water to ~125 ml)] with an aqueous solution of beryllium sulphate or nitrate (0.01 mole) dissolved in 10-20 ml water. The pH of the clear, yellow solution was adjusted to ~7 with dropwise addition of dilute ammonia (1:1). The yellow voluminous precipitate was converted into a crystalline easily filterable precipitate by digesting it on water bath for about an hour. The precipitate was

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filtered while hot on a sintered glass funnel, washed several times with water and finally with alcohol (15-20 ml portions) and ether and air dried.

The dried complex (m.p. $> 300^\circ$, decomp.) was analysed. Found : C, 70.05 ; H, 5.45 ; N, 9.94 ; Be, 3.2%. $\text{Be}(\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)$ requires : C, 69.81, H, 5.09 ; N, 10.19 ; Be, 3.28%. Beryllium-salen complexes were also prepared adopting the methods reported in the literature^{1,8} for comparative study.

Results and Discussion

N,N'-ethylenebis(salicylaldiminato) beryllium(II) is a yellow, crystalline compound, insoluble in almost all common organic solvents. It is soluble in trifluoroacetic acid to an appreciable extent. The complex does not melt up to 300° but decomposes above this temperature. The beryllium complex of 'Salen' prepared by reported methods also gave carbon, hydrogen values which correspond very nearly to 1 : 1 molarity but the beryllium value was always lower than the theoretical value in each case. Green and Alexander¹ have suggested dilute acid washing to remove the beryllium hydroxide present in the precipitate. It was observed that the acid washing slowly decomposes the complex. Further, it was found that the complex prepared by any of the methods reported^{1,8} does not contain any water of crystallisation. This was verified by repeating the precipitation of the complex several times adopting strictly the reported procedures and analyzing the samples and studying their ir spectra.

The ir spectrum of the ligand show a broad, weak band at $\sim 2650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributable to hydrogen bonded^{4,5}—OH. The spectrum of beryllium complex does not show the presence of any band in the region 3700 cm^{-1} - 2000 cm^{-1} due to either free or bonded OH stretching. This confirms the absence of free or bonded OH in the complex. The spectra of the ligand and the complex show strong bands in the region of 1600 - 1500 cm^{-1} attributable to the coupled vibrations^{4,6} of C=N and C=C. The ligand spectrum shows the characteristic strong band at 1280 cm^{-1} attributable to $\nu\text{CO} + \delta\text{ OH}$ vibration⁶. This band disappeared in the chelate and a new band is found at $\sim 1300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to bonded C—O stretching vibration. This confirms that the beryllium is bonded to ligand through phenolic OH groups. The participation of C=N group in bonding with beryllium is indicated by the shift of 1570 cm^{-1} band to 1540 cm^{-1} in the complex⁶. However, there appears to be a small peak at 1272 cm^{-1} in the complex spectrum which is presumably due to the presence of phenolic CO coupled with OH bending vibration. This observation further supports our finding that the presence of water molecule in beryllium complex is questionable. The spectrum below 1300 cm^{-1} show a number of bands due to the presence of ring vibrations, C—H in and out of plane deformation vibrations and metal-ligand vibrations. Furthermore, the pmr spectrum of the

beryllium complex does not show any signal due to OH proton either free or bonded. This finding further ruled out the presence of inter or intramolecularly bonded OH as proposed by Batley and Graddon². These authors have observed a band at 430 nm due to OH group in the reflectance spectrum of the complex. The beryllium-complex prepared by us does not show any absorption at 430 nm which again indicates absence of OH group in the complex. The thermogravimetric analysis of the beryllium complex does not show any loss in weight up to 200° . Progressive loss in weight does occur only on further heating. Perhaps this also indicates that the complex does not contain any water of crystallisation.

The previous authors^{1,2} have carried out model studies to justify their assumption to show that even though 'Salen' is a quadridentate ligand, it behaves as bidentate towards beryllium which does not tolerate even slight departure from tetrahedral stereochemistry. To verify this, we have also studied the model of beryllium-salen complex taking the bond distance⁷ of Be—O = 1.70 \AA and it was found that three bonds could easily be formed. When fourth bond is forced to form with the metal, the aromatic ring hydrogens are twisted out of the plane, increasing strain on the ring and consequently, leading to the rupture of ethylenic C—C bond.

Considering the above facts, the beryllium complex may be thought to have a polymeric structure in which 1 : 1 metal-ligand molarity is maintained. The insolubility of the complex in solvents perhaps indicate that the existence of a polymeric structure of the complex in which two or more metal-ligand molecules are bonded in such a way that the tetrahedral spacing between beryllium and the ligand is strictly maintained.

Mass spectrum of the complex showed molecular ion peak at $m/e\ 275$ ($\sim 25\%$) confirming the presence of a molecule in which beryllium and 'Salen' are in 1 : 1 molar ratio. This, however, does not rule out the polymeric structure proposed by us, since under drastic condition of high vacuum and high temperature, the polymeric units can break up and give rise to some monomers. Therefore, in the condensed solid state, the polymeric structure still seems to be feasible. This is also revealed by the departure of the analytical data slightly from the theoretical values. If we presume that the compound is polymeric, then we can account for all the four coordination numbers of beryllium ; however, in the monomeric compound the fourth coordination number remains unsatisfied and in this case one is allured to invoke the presence of a water molecule in order to have four coordinated beryllium.

We therefore feel that the composition and structure of beryllium-salen is not straightforward and the use of 'Salen' in gravimetric estimation of beryllium is not desirable.

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Stability Constants of Rhodizonic Acid Complexes in Solution

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THE studies of the metal complexes of rhodizonic acid have mostly been done by spectrophotometry¹⁻⁵, and studies by potentiometric method have not received sufficient attention. Therefore the present investigation was undertaken. In the present studies, stability constants of rhodizonic acid with divalent and trivalent metal ions Cu(II), Ni(II), Mn(II), Co(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), VO(II), UO₂(II), Ca(II), Mg(II), and Al(III) have been calculated by Bjerrum-Calvin's^{6,7} pH titration technique, employing Irving-Rossotti's formula⁸. The thermodynamic stability constants and free energy of formation of these complexes have also been evaluated.

Experimental

Rhodizonic acid (BDH, England), nitrate salt of copper(II), nickel(II), manganese(II), cobalt(II), vanadium(II), cadmium(II), uranyl(II) and aluminium(III) were employed for the studies. In case of magnesium(II) and calcium(II), the carbonates were dissolved in known amounts of nitric acid.

Metallic zinc (BDH, AnalaR) was dissolved in known volume of nitric acid, to obtain zinc(II) nitrate.

The metal contents were estimated by standard methods using EDTA titration⁹ wherever possible. All the metal nitrates were of BDH AnalaR quality.

Perchloric acid (Riedel), sodium perchlorate (Merck) and sodium hydroxide (BDH) were all used for the purpose.

All the solutions were prepared in double distilled water free from CO₂. pH measurements were done by a Philips pH meter using a glass calomel electrode assembly at a constant temperature 27 (± 0.02)° and ionic strength of 0.050M, 0.075M and 0.100M were maintained respectively in each case.

Procedure :

Solution mixture containing (a) acid (5 ml of 0.03M perchloric acid and 5 ml of 0.050M, 0.075M and 0.100M respectively of sodium perchlorate as the case may be), (b) ligand (mixture 'a' and 5 ml of 0.01M RA), (c) complex mixture 'b' and 5 ml of 0.005M metal solution were taken and total volume raised to 50 ml. The mixture (a), (b) and (c) were separately titrated against standard 0.1840M solution hydroxide solution.

Results and Discussion

Values of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL were calculated by Irving-Rossotti's formula. The formation curves corresponding to proton-ligand and metal-ligand equilibria were obtained by plotting \bar{n}_A and \bar{n} against pH and pL respectively.

The formation curves of the ligand extend between 0 and 2 on the \bar{n}_A scale, which supports the dissociation of the ligand in two steps, and this is shown as :

The values of the protonation constants of the ligand are given in Table 1. All calculations were done below the pH at which precipitation occurred.

It was noted that the addition of alkali was accompanied by a gradual change of colour of the ligand and chelate. The colour changes observed in presence of metal ions are almost similar to those observed in their absence. This signifies that metal complexes of similar colour are produced. Initially in an acidic medium, the colour of the ligand is yellowish-red, which gradually changes to red as alkali is added. In the metal-ligand systems also, the colour changed from yellowish-red with increase of pH , the changes being similar with those of the ligand alone.

During the titration of lead-RA system, precipitation occurred from the pH of separation, hence it was not possible to calculate the formation constants. Barium and strontium under the experimental conditions, do not appear to react with RA, as the chelate and ligand curves coincide.

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